

**International Conference on Science,
Technology, Engineering and Economy
ICOSTEE 2022**

Book of Abstracts

24 March 2022

Szeged

Hungary

Publisher:

Faculty of Engineering,

University of Szeged

ISBN 978-963-306-853-3

Publisher:

Assoc. prof. Dr. István Bíró
dean, head of department
University of Szeged Faculty of Engineering

Edited by:

István Bíró, Cecilia Hodúr, Zsuzsanna László, Szabolcs Kertész, Gábor Veréb,
Sándor Beszédes

Organizing Committee

Dr. Sándor Beszédes - assistant professor
Dr. József Csanádi - associate professor
Dr. Ferenc Farkas - senior research fellow
Dr. József Gál - associate professor
Dr. László Gogolák - assistant professor
Dr. Ernő Gyimes - associate professor
Zsuzsanna Hovorkáné dr Horváth - associate professor
Dr. Szabolcs Kertész - associate professor
Dr. Krisztián Kis - associate professor
Dr. Sándor Nagy - assistant professor
Katalin Pappné Dr Sziládi – associate professor
Dr. József Sárosi - associate professor
Dr. János Simon - associate professor
Dr. Balázs P. Szabó - associate professor
Dr. Gábor Veréb - research fellow
Dr. Anita Vidács – assistant professor

Members of Scientific Committee:

Prof. Dr Diána Bánáti – University of Szeged
Prof. dr. Katalin Bélafi-Bakó - Pannon University, Veszprém
Prof. Dr. Livia Cvetityánin - Óbuda University, Budapest / University of Novi Sad
Prof. Dr Gulsun Evrendilek - Izzet Baysal University, Bolu, Turkey
Prof. Dr Éva Gelencsér – Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Food Science Committee
Prof. Gilbert-Rainer Gillich - Babeş-Bolyai University, Romania
Prof. Yaodong Gu - Ningbo University, ChinaBI
Prof. Dr Cecília Hodúr – University of Szeged
Dr. Alexander Hošovský - Technical University of Košice, Slovakia
Prof. Dr. Zoltán Lakner – Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Science
Prof. Dr. Zsuzsanna László – University of Szeged
Prof. Dr. János Matúz - Cereal Research Non-profit Ltd.
Prof. Dr. Miklós Neményi - University of Győr
Prof. dr. József Popp - Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Science
Prof. Dr Beraat ÖZÇELİK - Istanbul Technical University, Turkey
Dr. Juvenal Rodríguez-Reséndiz - Universidad Autónoma de Querétaro, Mexico
Prof. Dr Zita Seres - University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Prof. Aleksander Sladkowski - University of Technology, Poland
Prof. Dr. István Szabó - Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences, Gödöllő
Prof. Dr. Antal Véha – University of Szeged

ENVIRONMENTALLY SAFE BIOMATERIALS FOR 3D PRINTING

Jovana Ugarković¹, Danijela Šuput¹, Nevena Hromiš¹, Mladena Lalić- Popović^{2,3}, Jelena Čanji Panić², Senka Popović¹

¹Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Bulevar Cara Lazara 1, 21 000 Novi Sad, Serbia

²Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

³Center for Medical and Pharmaceutical Investigations and Quality Control (CEMPhIC),
Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

jovana.ugarkovic@uns.ac.rs

ABSTRACT

Three-dimensional (3D) printing is a wide-ranging technique that can create complex structures and 3D objects for different purposes. This technique is also called additive manufacturing (AM), because it enables rapid prototyping, where according to digital view, model is formed by depositing material layer by layer. Different materials can be applied in this process, but not all of them are perspective and suitable in terms of protecting the environment. Biodegradable materials are better for the environment and can be used to replace non-biodegradable materials for this purpose. In the process of printing, biomaterials are being converted into the ink so that they can be used to print complex geometric structures. Mixtures of biopolymers with different properties are mostly used, thus forming ink of the desired characteristics. Before mixing the polymers, they need to be modified by appropriate processes in order to form the ink of desired characteristics. In this regard, mechanical, structural and rheological properties of printable biopolymeric-based materials and inks are discussed. The aim of this paper is to represent the current achievement in the field of 3D printing with an emphasis on environmentally safe biomaterials that can be used to produce well-defined 3D models with great preciseness.

Keywords: 3D printing, additive manufacturing, environmentally safe materials, biopolymers.